

Klein-Gordon Equation and Wave Function in Robertson-Walker and Schwarzschild space-time

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Abstract: In the general relativity theory, we find Klein-Gordon wave functions in Robertson-Walker and Schwarzschild space-time. Specially, this article is that Klein-Gordon wave equations is treated by gauge fixing equations in Robertson-Walker space-time and Schwarzschild space-time.

Keywords: General relativity theory, Klein-Gordon wave equations; Klein-Gordon wave functions; Robertson-Walker space-time; Schwarzschild space-time

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the general relativity theory, our article's aim is that we find Klein-Gordon wave equations and functions by gauge fixing equations in Robertson-Walker space-time and Schwarzschild space-time.

The gauge fixing equation in general relativity theory

$$A^{\mu}{}_{;\mu} = \frac{\partial A^{\mu}}{\partial X^{\mu}} + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} A^{\rho}$$

$$\rightarrow \partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} (A^{\rho} + \partial^{\rho} \Lambda)$$

$$= \partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} (A^{\rho} + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_{\sigma} \Lambda) \quad (1)$$

2. KLEIN-GORDON WAVE EQUATION IN ROBERTSON-WALKER SPACE-TIME

Because the gauge fixing equation is the electro-magnetic wave equation, Klein-Gordon wave equation is in Robertson-Walker space-time.

The Robertson-Walker solution is

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \quad (2)$$

In this time, 2-dimensional solution is

$$d\Omega = 0$$

$$d\tau^2 = dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} \quad (3)$$

The gauge fixing equation is in 2-dimensional solution[3]

$$\partial_{\mu} (A^{\mu} + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda) + \Gamma^{\mu}{}_{\mu\rho} (A^{\rho} + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_{\sigma} \Lambda)$$

$$= \partial_{\mu} A^{\mu} + \Gamma^{1}_{10} A^0 + \Gamma^{1}_{11} A^1 + \partial_{\mu} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\mu} \partial_{\nu} \Lambda + \Gamma^{1}_{10} g^{00} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial t} + \Gamma^{1}_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} \quad (4)$$

Hence, we can find Klein-Gordon wave equation in 2-dimensional Robertson-Walker space-time.

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_{\mu} g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\nu} \phi + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_{\mu} \partial_{\nu} \phi + \Gamma^{1}_{10} g^{00} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi + \Gamma^{1}_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \phi \\ &= \left[\frac{-2kr}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \frac{1-kr^2}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} - \frac{\dot{\Omega}}{c\Omega} \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \frac{kr}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right] \phi = \frac{m^2 c^4}{\hbar^2} \phi \\ & \Gamma^{1}_{10} = \frac{\dot{\Omega}}{c\Omega} \quad , \quad \Gamma^{1}_{11} = \frac{kr}{1-kr^2} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

In this time, we can think the shape of Klein-Gordon wave function from 2-dimentional Robertson-Walker space-time. In this case, light is

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau^2 &= dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \Omega^2(t) \frac{dr^2}{1-kr^2} = 0 \\ \int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} &= \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Hence, matter wave function is in 2-dimentional Robertson-Walker space-time.

$\phi = A_0 \exp i\Phi$, A_0 is amplitude

$$\Phi = \omega_0 \int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - k_0 \int \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}}, \quad \omega_0 \text{ is angular frequency, } k_0 = \left| \vec{k}_0 \right| \text{ is wave number}$$

$$\text{i) } k = 1, \Phi = \omega_0 \int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - k_0 \sin^{-1} r$$

$$\text{ii) } k = 0, \Phi = \omega_0 \int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - k_0 r$$

$$\text{iii) } k = -1, \Phi = \omega_0 \int \frac{dt}{\Omega(t)} - k_0 \sinh^{-1} r \quad (7)$$

If the definition of energy and momentum is

$$E = \frac{\hbar \omega_0}{\Omega(t)}, \vec{p} = \frac{\hbar \vec{k}_0}{\Omega^2(t)} \quad (8)$$

Energy-Momentum relation is in Robertson-Walker space-time,

$$m^2 c^4 = E^2 - \frac{\Omega^2(t)}{1-kr^2} p^2 c^2, E = m c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau}, \vec{p} = m \frac{d\vec{r}}{d\tau} \quad (9)$$

Finally, angular frequency-wave number relation is in Robertson-Walker space-time,

$$\frac{\hbar^2 \omega_0^2}{\Omega^2(t)} - \frac{\hbar^2 k_0^2 c^2}{\Omega^2(t)} \frac{1}{1-kr^2} = m^2 c^4 \quad (10)$$

Hence, Klein-Gordon wave equation-Eq(5) is satisfied by matter wave function-Eq(7) in Robertson-Walker space-time.

3. KLEIN-GORDON WAVE EQUATION IN SCHWARZSCHILD SPACE-TIME

Because the gauge fixing equation is the electro-magnetic wave equation, Klein-Gordon wave

equation is in Schwarzschild space-time.

The Schwarzschild solution is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} + r^2 d\Omega^2 \right] \quad (11)$$

In this time, 2-dimensional solution is

$$d\Omega = 0$$

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \quad (12)$$

The gauge fixing equation is in 2-dimensional solution[3]

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_\mu (A^\mu + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda) + \Gamma^\mu_{\mu\rho} (A^\rho + g^{\rho\sigma} \partial_\sigma \Lambda) \\ &= \partial_\mu A^\mu + \Gamma^0_{01} A^1 + \Gamma^1_{11} A^1 + \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Lambda + \Gamma^0_{01} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} + \Gamma^1_{11} g^{11} \frac{\partial \Lambda}{\partial r} \\ &= \partial_\mu A^\mu + \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \Lambda + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \Lambda \\ & \Gamma^0_{01} = \frac{GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}}, \quad \Gamma^1_{11} = -\frac{GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Hence, we can find Klein-Gordon wave equation in 2-dimensional Schwarzschild space-time.

$$\begin{aligned} & \partial_\mu g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\nu \phi + g^{\mu\nu} \partial_\mu \partial_\nu \phi \\ &= \left[\frac{2GM}{r^2 c^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} - \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} + \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} \right] \phi = \frac{m^2 c^4}{\hbar^2} \phi \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

In this time, we can think the shape of Klein-Gordon wave function from 2-dimensional Schwarzschild space-time. In this case, light is

$$d\tau^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) dt^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} = 0$$

$$t = \frac{1}{c} \int \frac{dr}{1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}} = \frac{r}{c} + \frac{2GM}{c^3} \ln \left| r - \frac{2GM}{c^2} \right| \quad (15)$$

Hence, Klein-Gordon wave function is in 2-dimensional Schwarzschild space-time-

$$\phi = A_0 \exp i\Phi, A_0 \text{ is amplitude}$$

$$\Phi = \omega_0 t - k_0 r - k_0 \frac{2GM}{c^2} \ln \left| r - \frac{2GM}{c^2} \right|$$

$$\omega_0 \text{ is angular frequency, } k_0 = \left| \vec{k}_0 \right| \text{ is wave number} \quad (16)$$

If the definition of energy and momentum is

$$E = \frac{\hbar \omega_0}{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)}, \vec{p} = \hbar \vec{k}_0 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) \quad (17)$$

Energy-Momentum relation is in Schwarzschild space-time,

$$m^2 c^4 = \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) E^2 - \frac{p^2 c^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)}, E = m c^2 \frac{dt}{d\tau}, \vec{p} = m \frac{d\vec{r}}{d\tau} \quad (18)$$

Finally, angular frequency-wave number relation is in Schwarzschild space-time,

$$\frac{\hbar^2 \omega_0^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right)} - \hbar^2 k_0^2 \left(1 - \frac{2GM}{rc^2}\right) = m^2 c^4 \quad (19)$$

Hence, Klein-Gordon wave equation-Eq(14) is satisfied by matter wave function-Eq(16) in Schwarzschild space-time

4. CONCLUSION

We find Klein-Gordon wave equation and function in Robertson-Walker space-time. We find Klein-Gordon wave equation and function in Schwarzschild space-time..

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